

CSIRO SYMPOSIUM ON COMPUTATIONAL CHALLENGES IN LIFE SCIENCES

12-13 MAY 1994 MELBOURNE

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PROGRAMMED INSTRUCTIONS

FOR THE IBM 7090

CSIRO SYMPOSIUM ON "COMPUTATIONAL CHALLENGES IN LIFE SCIENCES"

ORGANIZED BY

CSIRO SFUMC* AND THE CSIRO SUPERCOMPUTING SUPPORT GROUP

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Dr Tom Spurling, CSIRO Division of Chemicals and Polymers

Dr Mike Rickard, CSIRO Division of Animal Health

Dr Marek Michalewicz, CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group (Secretary)

Organising Committee:

Dr John O'Callaghan (CSIRO Division of Information Technology - Chair)
and members of CSIRO SFUMC,

Dr Marek Michalewicz (CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group - Secretary)

* Supercomputing Facility Users Management Committee

PROGRAMME

Thursday 12 May 1994

0800 - 0840 Registration of Delegates and Morning Coffee
The Clunies-Ross Conference Centre Foyer

SESSION 1 - Chair: John O'Callaghan

0840 - 0845	Welcome and Opening Address: Peter Colman Chief, Division of Biomolecular Engineering, CSIRO, Australia
0845 - 0930	Overview of the First World Congress on Computational Medicine, Public Health and Biotechnology Matthew Witten Dept. Applications Research & Development, University of Texas Centre for High Performance Computing
0930 - 1015	Application of Molecular Dynamics and Free Energy Perturbation Calculations to Organic and Biochemical Systems Peter Kollman University of California at San Francisco
1015- 1045	Morning Refreshments

SESSION 2 - Chair: Peter Colman

1045 - 1130	Xray Macromolecular Structure Refinement by Molecular Dynamics Simulation Jose Vargese Biomolecular Research Institute, CSIRO, Australia
1130 - 1215	NMR, Protein Structure and Drug Design Ray Norton Biomolecular Research Institute, CSIRO, Australia
1215 - 1300	Prediction of Three-Dimensional Protein Structures Based on Homology Herbert Treutlein Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, Australia
1300 - 1430	Luncheon

SESSION 3 - Chair: Peter Kollman

1430 - 1515	Supercomputing Studies of Biological Membranes: Drug Diffusion and Integral Membrane Protein Structure Terry Stouch Bristol-Myers Squibb, USA
1515 - 1600	Computational Studies of Enzyme Mechanism Brian Smith Biomolecular Research Institute, CSIRO, Australia
1600 -1630	Afternoon Refreshments

SESSION 4 - Chair: Tom Spurling

1630 - 1715	Supercomputing for Research and Development: Drug Discovery and Design in the Pharmaceutical Environment Dennis Underwood Merck, USA
1715 - 1800	QSAR and Neural Networks in Life Sciences David Winkler CSIRO Division of Chemicals and Polymers, Australia

1930

CONFERENCE DINNER

Friday 13 May 1994

0830 - 0845 Morning Coffee

SESSION 5 - Chair: John Furness

0845 - 0930	Life Science Applications on Cray Supercomputers World-wide Robert A Eades Cray Research, Inc. USA
0930 - 1015	Computational and Mathematical Gerontology Matthew Witten Dept. Applications Research and Development, University of Texas Centre for High Performance Computing
1015 - 1100	The Use of High Speed Computing in Radiation Therapy Treatment Planning of Cancer Patients Julian Rosenman University of North Carolina, USA

1100 - 1130 Morning Refreshments

SESSION 6 - Chair: Matthew Witten

1130 - 1215	Three-dimensional Computation of Blood Flow in the Heart Charles S Peskin Courant Institute of Mathematical Sciences, New York University, USA
1215 - 1300	Modelling and Visualization of Biological Structures in a Virtual Laboratory Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz University of Calgary, Canada & Division of Entomology, CSIRO, Australia

1300 - 1430 Luncheon

SESSION 7 - Chair: Adrian Gibbs

1430 - 1515	Realistic Models of Nervous Systems: Are They Achievable and Will They Be Useful? John B Furness The University of Melbourne
1515 - 1600	Simulation of Electrocortical Waves Using Anatomical Estimates of Synaptic Density Jim Wright Neuroscience Laboratory, Swinburne University of Technology, Victoria, Australia

1600 - 1630 Afternoon Refreshments

SESSION 8 - Chair: Jim Wright

1630 - 1645	Supercomputing for You in Australia Robert Bell Manager, CSIRO Supercomputing Facility, Australia
1645 - 1700	CLOSING ADDRESS John O'Callaghan Chief, Division of Information Technology, CSIRO, Australia

SOFTWARE DEMONSTRATIONS AND EXHIBITIONS

AUDITORIUM 2

AUDITORIUM 3

FRONT ROOM:
"BANK"

Thursday 12 May			
<i>Open all day</i>	UniChem StorageTek	Biosym	STNInternational
10:15-10:45		Virtual Plants	
11:00-11:30		Plexus	
14:00-14:30	Teijin-MSI		
18:00-18:30		Genesis	
18:30-19:00			Mapmaker
Friday 13 May			
<i>Open all day</i>	Teijin-MSI StorageTek	Plexus	Mapmaker STNInternational
11:00-11:30	UniChem		
11:00-12:15		X-PLOR	
14:00-14:30		Biosym	
14:30-16:15		3D&4D NMR	

Exhibitions and demonstrations:

Auditorium 2, Auditorium 3, and Bank (front room).

	Location	Product	Supplier	Demonstrator	Affiliation
1	Aud 2. A	<i>UniChem</i>	Cray Research Inc	Dr Marek T. Michalewicz	CSIRO SSG
2	Aud 3. E	<i>BIOSYM</i>	BIOSYM	Dr Anneliese Palmer, Dr Cliff Holloway	BIOSYM
3	Aud 2. B	<i>MSI</i>	MSI	Dr Thomas Hoeffel	Teijin / Molecular Simulations, Inc.
4	Aud 3. F – Thurs	<i>Genesis</i>		Dr David Liley	Swinburne University of Technology
5	Aud 3. J – Thurs	<i>Virtual Plants</i>		Dr Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz	CSIRO Div. Entomology
6	Aud 3. J – Fri	<i>X-PLOR</i>		Dr Jose Varghese	Biomolecular Research Institute
7	Bank. H	<i>Mapmaker</i>		Dr Evans Lagudah	CSIRO Division of Plant Industry
8	Aud 3. F – Fri	<i>3D&4D NMR software</i>		Dr Ray Norton	Biomolecular Research Institute
9	Aud 3. G	<i>Plexus</i>		Dr Hugh Kelly	University of Melbourne
10	Bank. I	<i>STN International</i>	CSIRO ISB	Fatma Ahmet	CSIRO ISB
11	Aud 2. D	<i>StorageTek 9360 WolfCreek Automated Cartridge System</i>	StorageTek	Mr Roger Minnett	StorageTek Australia

CONFERENCE BUILDING FLOOR PLAN

GROUND FLOOR

WELCOME TO THE SYMPOSIUM

On behalf of the organising Committee, we would like to welcome you to this Symposium.

This is a *first* for the CSIRO Supercomputing Facilities Users Management Committee, a *first* for the CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group, and a *first* in bringing the theme of computation into the field of Life Sciences in Australia.

The organisers had a vision of what computational methods could achieve in the Life Sciences, having seen the benefits of the use of High Performance Computation in other areas of science, and having seen glimpses of what was being done in other parts of the world. The announcement of the First World Congress On Computational Medicine, Public Health and Biotechnology held in Austin, Texas, 24-28 April, 1994 was the starting point for this Symposium, and it is especially good to welcome Matthew Witten, the driving force behind that Congress to this Symposium.

We particularly welcome all our overseas guests, and thank them for agreeing to come.

We thank our sponsors, without whose help and support we would not have been able to attempt this Symposium.

We thank our demonstrators and suppliers, for preparing and displaying their software and products.

We welcome all the other speakers, and all of the attendees to this Symposium. We hope you find it valuable and inspirational. Please make the most of the presentations, and also the displays and demonstrations in Auditoria 2 and 3, and the Front Room.

We wish to thank the administrative staff of the CSIRO Division of Information Technology, Melbourne Lab; especially Sue Wilson, Heather Vile, Vicky Williams and Jim Taylor for their excellent support and help during all stages of preparation of the conference.

John O'Callaghan and Marek Michalewicz

For the Organising Committee

SPEAKERS' BIOGRAPHIES AND ABSTRACTS

MATTHEW WITTEN

BIOGRAPHY

Matthew Witten, a native of Boston, obtained his A.B. (mathematics and physics) at Boston University. After receiving an M.S. in mathematical physics at Indiana University Bloomington, and an M.S. and Ph.D. in mathematical biology/medicine at SUNY at Buffalo, Center for Theoretical Biology, he spent postdoctoral research time at the Department of Biometry, Medical University of South Carolina and the Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California. He has held faculty positions at the University of California Santa Barbara (Mathematics), Illinois Institute of Technology (Mathematics), University of Louisville School of Medicine (Community Medicine) jointly with the University of Louisville Speed Scientific School of Engineering and Mathematics, as well as the University of Minnesota-Minneapolis (Computer Science). He is currently Head of the Department of Applications Research and Development at the University of Texas System Center For High Performance Computing, where he serves as Associate Director of the Center as well. In addition, he holds an appointment as Associate Professor of Physiology at the University of Texas Health Science Center San Antonio, and Associate Professor of Biomedical Engineering at the University of Texas at Austin. His research interests lie in the study of aging processes at all levels of biological organization. Much of his work has been done in cellular population modeling with respect to studying the problem of cancer-aging dynamics. More recently, he has extended his interests into two specific areas, methodologies for studying high dimensional complex datasets and computational medicine/public health.

These applications areas tend to be computationally intensive, to require sophisticated visualization techniques (audio, visual, sensory), and to offer an abundance of research problems here-to-fore intractable with respect to the lack of biological/clinical understanding, computational power, and analytical tools and techniques.

**OVERVIEW OF THE FIRST WORLD
CONGRESS ON COMPUTATIONAL
MEDICINE, PUBLIC HEALTH AND
BIOTECHNOLOGY
(AUSTIN, TEXAS, 24-28 APRIL, 1994)**

Dr Matthew Witten

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ABSTRACT

We will examine the emerging transdiscipline of Computational Medicine, Public Health and Biotechnology. This talk will provide and introductory overview of the field and its wonderful variety of truly exciting research efforts. We will examine some of the issues that arise should one wish to play in this field. And we will close with a summary of the events at the First World Congress On Computational Medicine, Public Health, and Biotechnology held in Austin Texas, 24-28 April 1994. No technical expertise is required for attendance at this talk.

PETER KOLLMAN

BIOGRAPHY

B.A. Grinnell College, Grinnell, Iowa, 1966; Ph.D. Princeton University, 1970; NATO Postdoctoral Fellow, Cambridge England, 1970-71; on the faculty at University of California San Francisco Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry since 1971, where I am now Professor of Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Chemistry. My research has centered on computational chemistry of molecular interactions using quantum mechanical and molecular mechanical methodologies.

**THE APPLICATION OF MOLECULAR
DYNAMICS AND FREE ENERGY
PERTURBATION CALCULATIONS
TO ORGANIC AND BIOCHEMICAL
SYSTEMS.**

Dr Peter Kollman

Professor of Chemistry and
Pharmaceutical Chemistry,
Department of Pharmaceutical
Chemistry; University of California, San
Francisco.

e-mail: pak@cgl.ucsf.edu

ABSTRACT

We will present recent results and perspectives on molecular dynamics and free energy calculations to model systems (solvation of small solutes in water), ionophore-ion recognition, protein-ligand interactions and nucleic acid-ligand interactions. The ability of the simulations to reproduce experimental free energies, give insights and make predictions will be critically assessed.

JOSE VARGHESE

BIOGRAPHY

Dr J N Varghese was born in Nairobi Kenya in 1949. He has lived in Australia since 1963.

B.Sc. (Hons) Theoretical Physics
University of Queensland 1969.

Ph.D. Physics, X-ray scattering,
University of Western Australia 1973.

ARGC Fellow, Charge Density Studies,
University of Western Australia 1974-
76.

Lecturer, School of Molecular Sciences,
Polarized Neutron Scattering,
University of Sussex, U.K. 1977-80.

CSIRO Post Doctoral Fellow, Protein
Crystallography, Melbourne 1980-84.

Currently Senior Principal Research
Scientist, Biomolecular Research
Institute, Parkville.

**X-RAY MACROMOLECULAR STRUCTURE
REFINEMENT BY MOLECULAR
DYNAMICS SIMULATION.**

Dr Jose Varghese

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing requirement in recent years for high speed computing facilities to cope with analysing the results of X-ray structural studies of biological macromolecules with the view of developing enabling technology for the engineering of proteins and nucleic acids, and in the design of

pharmaceuticals. Techniques utilising the rapid convergence properties of 'simulated annealing' procedures by molecular dynamics will be discussed in association with molecular structure refinement of X-ray diffraction data.

Studies conducted on the determination of the structure of an Influenza Virus antigen and complexes with inhibitors that have led to possible antiviral drugs by rational design will illustrate this technique.

RAY NORTON

BIOGRAPHY

Ray NORTON was born in Melbourne and completed a B.Sc. (Honours) degree in biochemistry at the University of Melbourne in 1970. He then moved to the Australian National University in Canberra to undertake a PhD in chemistry under the supervision of Dr Howard Bradbury. In 1974 he took up a post-doctoral fellowship at Indiana University, returning to Australia in 1976 with the support of a Queen Elizabeth Fellowship at the Roche Research Institute of Marine Pharmacology in Sydney. Following completion of this Fellowship he was appointed as a research scientist at RRIMP. He accepted a faculty position in the School of Biochemistry at the University of New South Wales in 1981. In 1992 he moved to his current position as Head of the NMR Laboratory and Assistant Director of the newly-formed Biomolecular Research Institute in Melbourne.

Dr Norton is a Professorial Associate of the University of Melbourne. While at the University of New South Wales he held visiting appointments at the Universities of Oxford (1985-1986) and Washington (1989-1990). He is a member of the editorial boards of the *Journal of Biomolecular NMR* and *Toxicon* and has served on regional grant interviewing committees for the NH&MRC. He is a member of the Australian Society for Biochemistry & Molecular Biology, the Australian Society for Biophysics, and the International Society of Toxicology, and is currently the Victorian representative for the ASB.

His research interests lie in the area of protein structure and function, especially of pharmacologically active

toxins and cytokines, structure-based drug design and NMR spectroscopy. His group has solved the three-dimensional structures of a number of polypeptides and proteins, including several ion-channel toxins, a malarial surface antigen and insulin-like growth factor II.

NMR, PROTEIN STRUCTURE AND DRUG DESIGN

Dr Ray Norton

NMR Laboratory, Biomolecular Research Institute, 381 Royal Parade, Parkville 3052

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ABSTRACT

As a means of determining the complete three-dimensional structure of a protein, NMR is a relatively new approach, the first protein structures having been determined by this means in 1985. Since then there has been a rapid growth in this field, facilitated by improvements in both NMR spectrometers and the computational methods used to relate NMR data to three-dimensional structure. The great advantage of NMR over more traditional methods for biopolymer structure determination is that the molecules are studied in solution without the need for crystallization. This enables NMR to be applied to a wide range of molecules in a variety of physical environments. It also makes it well suited to characterising the structural changes that may occur in analogues of a protein generated by site-directed mutagenesis or synthesis, and thus to elucidating the structure-function relationships of that protein.

Although already a powerful method for protein structure determination, NMR has the potential for substantial further development in this field. This will come about through improvements in spectrometer hardware and software (the first 750MHz spectrometers are currently being installed in the USA and Europe), the development of new methods for data acquisition, improved computational methods for data

analysis and structure determination, and automation of various steps in the overall procedure.

Examples of the application of NMR methods to determining the three-dimensional structures of proteins will be provided from our work on pharmacologically active toxins that modulate ion channel function (1, 2). The way in which structural information can be used in the subsequent design of therapeutics based on these toxins will be discussed. Opportunities for facilitating and enhancing the computational components of these processes will also be considered.

1. Pallaghy, P.K., Duggan, B.M., Pennington, M.W. & Norton, R.S. (1993) The three-dimensional structure in solution of the calcium channel blocker ω -conotoxin. *J. Mol. Biol.* 234, 405-420.
2. Wilcox, G.R., Fogh, R.H. & Norton, R.S. (1993) Refined structure in solution of the sea anemone neurotoxin ShI. *J. Biol. Chem.* 268, 24707-24719.

HERBERT TREUTLEIN

BIOGRAPHY

Born in Schweinfurt/Main in Germany.

1978-1984 study of physics at the Technische Universität, München, Germany.

1988 PhD (Dr. rer. nat) in physics from the Technische Universität, München, Germany. Title of thesis: *Molecular Dynamics Simulations of the Photosynthetic Reaction Center of Rps. Viridis.*

1989 Postdoctoral position at the Beckman Institute and the Dept. of Physics, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, USA. Main project: Study of the influence of protein environment on electron transfer in the photosynthetic reaction center of *Rps. viridis*.

1989-1992 Postdoctoral position at the Department of Molecular Biophysics and Biochemistry, Yale University, New Haven, USA. Main Project: Computer simulations of helix association in membranes.

Since 1992: Head of the Molecular Modelling Group, Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, Parkville, Victoria. Main Projects: Modelling studies of growth factors and their receptors, homology modelling and development force field parameters for molecular mechanics calculations.

PREDICTION OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL PROTEIN STRUCTURES BASED ON HOMOLOGY.

Dr H R Treutlein

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge of the detailed three-dimensional structure of a protein is often essential for the understanding of its function. The experimental determination of a protein's tertiary structure by X-ray crystallography or NMR spectroscopy is still a very time consuming process, and in some cases even impossible. In contrast, determination of the amino acid sequences of proteins is a much simpler task.

Since general rules for the folding of proteins have not yet been discovered, it is still not possible to predict the three-dimensional structure of a protein from its sequence alone. A prediction becomes more feasible, however, if more data is known about the protein.

Modelling the tertiary structure of a protein based on its homology to proteins with already known structures is becoming one of the few methods where detailed structural information of a protein can be gained from its amino acid sequence. The method relies on the observation that proteins with similar sequence and secondary structure will adopt a similar three-dimensional fold.

During the talk homology modelling studies of the *Interleukin-6* (IL-6) and *Leukaemia Inhibitory Factor* (LIF) will be presented. Both proteins belong to a family of cytokines which basic three-

dimensional structure is formed by a four-helical bundle. During the recent years X-ray crystal and/or NMR structures have become available for some of the members of the four-helical bundle cytokine family which form the basis of our IL-6 and LIF modelling. Sequence alignment of proteins with unknown and known structure is the first and a rather crucial step in the process of homology modelling. Having aligned the sequences, two approaches to build a protein structure will be presented:

(i) A "classical" method using the HOMOLOGY program where coordinates of side chains of conserved regions of G-CSF are mapped to unknown coordinates of corresponding sidechains.

(ii) In a second method less emphasis is given to sequence alignment. Here, the model is constructed using a simulated annealing method similar to procedures employed in NMR refinement. This method is based on conserved distances between corresponding amino acids in G-CSF and other cytokines.

Structures created by both methods are refined by further simulated annealing procedures. A final refinement step also includes layers of water molecules surrounding the proteins.

The quality of the models is checked by assessing the stereo-chemical properties of the final structures and comparing structural features with experimental data, eg from 2-dimensional NMR or site-directed mutagenesis.

In some simple cases it is still sometimes possible to predict protein structures, even when only little experimental data is known. An example will be shown at the end of the talk where the structure of the transmembrane region of the

Glycophorin A (GpA) dimer was predicted based on its amino acid sequence, its secondary structure and results of site-directed mutagenesis. The modelling results in conjunction with the experimental studies led to the discovery of a more general sequence motif which can also induce dimerization of transmembrane helices in proteins other than GpA.

TERRY STOUCH

BIOGRAPHY

Terry Stouch is a Senior Research Investigator in the Macromolecular Structure Division of the Bristol-Myers Squibb Pharmaceutical Research Institute in Princeton, NJ. In the Department of Macromolecular Modeling, he uses supercomputing techniques to study large biological molecules and biomolecular complexes and studies methods of computer aided drug design. Prior to this, he was a research scientist in the X-ray protein crystallography laboratory at the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) in Washington D.C. and an independent consultant in computer-aided drug design and patenting issues.

Under an Office of Naval Technology Postdoctoral Fellowship in the Laboratory for the Structure of Matter at the NRL, he pioneered some of the first supercomputing simulations of biological membranes, which he continues in studies of membrane permeation by drugs and in studies of the structure and dynamics of integral membrane proteins.

Both his Ph.D. in chemistry and B.S. in biochemistry were earned at the Pennsylvania State University. His research interests include studies of molecular "potential energy functions" (for molecular modeling and molecular dynamics simulations), studies of molecular electrostatics, computer simulations of biomolecules, and methods of computer aided drug design, including pattern recognition, statistical analysis, database search, and molecular comparison.

**SUPERCOMPUTING STUDIES OF
BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES:
DRUG DIFFUSION AND INTEGRAL
MEMBRANE PROTEIN STRUCTURE.**

Dr Terry Stouch

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ABSTRACT

Biological (lipid bilayer) membranes play pivotal roles in a great many of life's important processes. They maintain the integrity of cells and organelles by regulating the passage of molecules from one side to the other. They also serve as a site of action of many important proteins and enzymes: G-protein coupled receptors that moderate the function of many hormones; phospholipases, which are important in inflammation; ion channels, which regulate nerve function; and portions of the immune system, to name just a few.

An understanding of biomembranes is clearly important for understanding and regulating physiology. Unfortunately, these biological constructs are very fluid and delicate and are difficult to study experimentally.

We have successfully applied supercomputer-based methods to model biomembranes at the atomic level. Through molecular dynamics simulations we include motion and fluidity, which largely determine membrane structure and properties. These simulations can duplicate much of what we know about biomembranes

from experiment and give us confidence in our approach. More importantly, they also give us the atomic level insight that is often missing from experiment. This insight helps us to better understand the results of experiments and give us new information about biomembranes.

We have used the dynamical models to study the diffusion of small molecules within the membranes and, hence, have learned important lessons pertaining to the permeation of biomembranes by drugs, important to bioavailability and the prediction of drug efficacy.

Transmembrane proteins have also been incorporated into these models and simulation is helping us to understand the structure and dynamics of the integral membrane proteins mentioned above.

BRIAN SMITH

BIOGRAPHY

Brian Smith was born in 1960 in Melbourne, Australia.

Dr Smith was educated at the University of Melbourne, completing his Ph.D. studies in 1987, and a Postgraduate Diploma in Mathematical Studies in 1993. He spent four years at the Research School of Chemistry, Australian National University, initially as a postdoctoral fellow and subsequently as a Research Officer.

In 1991 he returned to Melbourne as Research Scientist (Computational Chemist) in the Diffraction and Theory group at the Biomolecular Research Institute, to study the mechanism of enzymes.

He has published widely on the application of quantum-mechanical methods in the determination of molecular structure, reaction mechanism and molecular properties.

COMPUTATIONAL STUDIES OF ENZYME MECHANISM

Dr Brian Smith

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ABSTRACT

Enzymes are the biological catalysts responsible for nearly all biochemical reactions that comprise life. An understanding of the mechanisms by which they achieve their enormous rate acceleration is therefore of great importance.

The study of many features of enzymes, and proteins in general, can be achieved with classical mathematical treatments; however, any issue regarding covalent-bond breaking and making necessitates the use of some form of Quantum Mechanical description of the atoms involved in the enzymatic process. A knowledge of the energetics of substrate binding, intermediates and transition states along the reaction pathway provide a detailed insight into the role of the enzyme.

Quantum mechanical methods have been applied to the study of the mechanism of the human influenza virus surface protein, neuraminidase. This protein is responsible for elution of newly synthesised virions from infected cells, and therefore ensuring progeny survival. Its function is to cleave terminal α -ketosidically linked sialic acid on glycolipids or glycoproteins. The general procedure of acid hydrolysis of carbohydrates along with uncatalysed hydrolysis of sialic acid is investigated. We also consider the effects of mutation in the protein on the

mechanism and also upon the binding of inhibitors.

DENNIS UNDERWOOD

BIOGRAPHY

I gained my Ph.D. in Physical Organic Chemistry under Prof. John Bowie at Adelaide University in 1981. I continued my studies in gas-phase ion chemistry using a FAB device designed and constructed at Rockefeller University under the supervision of Prof. Frank Field. While still at Rockefeller University I was awarded a CSIRO Postdoctoral Award to investigate the electronic structure of organometallic complexes and solid state materials with Prof. Roald Hoffmann at Cornell University. This was my introduction into computational chemistry.

After nearly 2 years in Prof. Hoffmann's laboratory, I moved back to Australia to the CSIRO Division of Applied Organic Chemistry in Dr. Tom Spurling's laboratory - I continued the work that I had begun at Cornell.

In 1985 my education in computational chemistry continued at the Australian National University in Prof. Leo Radom's laboratory where I studied the electronic structure of novel, transient organics using ab initio molecular orbital theory.

At the end of 1985 I returned to the USA to a position in the molecular modeling group led by Dr Peter Gund at the Merck Research Laboratories where I have been since that time. During this period I have risen to leader of the molecular modeling applications staff. My responsibilities include the scientific direction and project coordination for some 8 senior scientific personnel in addition to a number of scientific collaborations inside and outside Merck. I continue to be interested in using molecular structure and

calculations to understand chemical and biochemical reaction and interactions and I am excited by the recent advances in our understanding and our treatment of the intrinsically complex biological processes involved in disease and therapy.

SUPERCOMPUTING FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT: DRUG DISCOVERY AND DESIGN IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL ENVIRONMENT

Dennis J Underwood, Kristine Prendergast, Simon K Kearsley, Michael Miller, Robert Sheridan, Catherine D Strader, Tung M Fong, Arthur A Patchett

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ABSTRACT

Our understanding of the complex nature of biological systems often begins with a simple cartoon which describes in the coarsest terms the molecular players and the interactions between them which bring about a biological response. Biological research is directed towards identifying and characterizing the players which, in a cause and effect manner, initiate, control and participate in complex biological pathways. As each biochemical pathway of the disease state is understood and the role of key *molecular players* in this process identified, attempts are made to correct imbalances by interfering with the biological process at the molecular level.

The strategies that are used to identify and design potential drugs depend on the degree of detail known about the disease process. Broadly speaking the categories are: virtually nothing is known about the players and the events leading to disease; much of the biochemistry is understood and there is a structure activity relationship (SAR) for classes of compounds affecting the disease; much is known about the

mechanism and also about the structure and interactions of the biochemical targets. At our simplest level of understanding described above directed chemical screening is the most effective approach. We will discuss computational methods that we have developed in the area of *database mining*. As detailed biochemical, medicinal chemical and structural information becomes available the directed screening strategy, although still *fuzzy* in its approach, becomes better determined and as a result more computationally intensive. We will describe our approaches in using the available information such as SAR to develop pharmacophore models and how this is used in both design and mining. Finally we will describe our efforts using information from structurally well defined protein targets to develop pharmacologic agents. Problems having little information might be considered, at this stage, as computationally futile. As the information content of the system increases the problem becomes computationally feasible. The range of questions which can be addressed by calculations for systems having a high information content (good structural information, plenty of SAR, etc.) is growing rapidly.

DR DAVID WINKLER

QSAR and NEURAL NETWORKS IN LIFE SCIENCES

Dr David A Winkler

Principal Research Scientist
CSIRO Division of Chemicals and
Polymers, Clayton, Australia

e-mail: dave@carbon.chem.csiro.au

ABSTRACT

In the past several years a number of interesting new computer technologies, analysis techniques and molecular design methods of importance in life sciences have emerged. The enormous increases in computational power which have occurred in the last decade have made this possible, and have facilitated human interaction with molecular information systems.

The acquisition of biodata and exchange of ideas has greatly benefited from the expansion of international computer networks such as the Internet. Facilities such as chemical interest groups, electronic mail, telnet and FTP access, WWW and WAIS servers are becoming increasingly important in biomedical research. The efficient storage and retrieval of molecular information has been facilitated by the availability of small molecule, protein and sequence databases, coupled with efficient database searching algorithms.

At the level of design of bioactive molecules, these developments have improved the utilization of existing chemical compounds as new molecular design leads. New molecular design tools, such as similarity measures, neural networks, 3-D QSAR methods and protein homology and motif modelling, have proven very useful for understanding relationships between

biological activity and molecular structure.

In other areas of life sciences, neural networks are becoming increasingly useful for understanding neural function, in imaging and in pattern recognition.

This lecture discusses the applications of neural networks to life sciences and 3-D QSAR (molecular field analysis) to bioactive molecule design. These new techniques will be illustrated by examples of their application to medicine and crop protection.

ROBERT A. EADES

BIOGRAPHY

Robert A. Eades joined Cray Research in December 1987 as a Quantum Chemist and directed the efforts of the Chemical Research and Engineering Group until March of 1992, when he became the Director of Industry Marketing for the Chemical, Pharmaceutical, Materials & Electronics Industries. His activities focus on the development and support of computational methods for molecular biology, chemistry, chemical engineering, and materials science along with the use of these methods in solving R&D problems in the chemical, pharmaceutical, and materials based industries. Prior to joining Cray Research, Robert was a Senior Research Chemist at the Allied-Signal Engineered Materials Research Centre where his research activities focused on the development and application of computational chemistry methods in the areas of heterogeneous catalysis, synthetic polymers, the design of advanced jet fuels, and surface segregation in alloys. He was a member of the Theoretical Chemistry Group at Argonne National Laboratory for five years before joining Allied-Signal, and has held Guest Research Scientist appointments at Lawrence Berkeley, Argonne, and Brookhaven National Laboratories. Robert currently holds a Guest Research Scientist appointment in the Theoretical Chemistry Group at Los Alamos National Laboratory, with a USDOE Q security clearance. Robert is author or co-author of more than 50 scientific and technical publications and numerous lectures on the application and development of quantum chemistry methods in chemistry and materials science research. He was also principal editor and co-author of a USDOE assessment of the status and capabilities of molecular structure-based theoretical methods to accurately model the chemical

and physical properties of heterogeneous catalysts, tri-biological materials, and the adhesion of materials.

HARNESSING SUPERCOMPUTERS FOR PHARMACEUTICAL AND BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Dr Robert A. Eades
Cray Research, Inc.
655-A Lone Oak Drive
Eagan, MN 55121 USA

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ABSTRACT

Supercomputers have been work-horses for computational chemistry applications in pharmaceutical research for many years now. Wide numbers of researchers in both industry and academia currently rely upon them to produce their results as they search for new drugs.

However, these are not the only applications of supercomputers within the life sciences. Traditional engineering applications are also finding increasing usage.

Computational fluid dynamics methods are being used to simulate blood flow and to design the chemical reactors which are used to produce pharmaceuticals. Some companies are also using sophisticated dynamic process simulation methods to help design their production facilities to run more efficiently, and profitably.

Examples of these types of applications on CRAY supercomputers will be presented and discussed.

COMPUTATIONAL AND MATHEMATICAL GERONTOLOGY

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UT System Center For High Performance Computing
Balcones Research Center, 1.154 CMS
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USA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this presentation is to examine some of the important mathematical and computational issues that arise in the study of the biological and clinical aspects of the aging process. We will organize the talk around the various levels of organization of an organism, from molecular through population. No background in geriatrics or gerontology is required.

JULIAN ROSENMAN

BIOGRAPHY

Born: 24 July 1945, Cleveland, Ohio

Education

June, 1977

M.D., The University of Texas Health Science Center, Southwestern Medical School, Dallas, Texas

Dec., 1971

Ph.D. in physics, The University of Texas, Austin, Texas

Employment

Currently a Professor of Radiation Oncology and Computer Science, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, NC.

Grant Participation:

10 grants over the last 6 years

Publications:

Approximately 120 journal and proceedings articles, abstracts and book chapters.

Presentations:

Approximately 70 invited scientific presentations.

THE USE OF HIGH SPEED COMPUTING IN RADIATION THERAPY TREATMENT PLANNING OF CANCER PATIENTS.

Julian Rosenman, MD, Ph.D.

Professor of Radiation Oncology and Computer Science University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, NC

e-mail: rosenman@radonc.unc.edu

ABSTRACT

Radiation therapy is one of the three major methods of treating cancer, the other two being surgery and chemotherapy. Although x-rays have been used therapeutically since the turn of the century, rapid improvements in treatment planning and delivery have come only recently. One of the most important advances in radiation treatment planning, modeling the patient with high fidelity in 3D, has only been possible with the advent of reasonably priced high-speed computers and graphics hardware.

To illustrate how high speed computers can be used in the treatment of cancer with radiation I would like to present the case of a 22 year old male who was recently seen in our department. Two years ago this young man had brain tumor of a type that is usually curable. The tumor was surgically removed with a frontal approach and the patient was treated with postoperative radiation covering only the posterior 2/3 of the brain. The patient then moved to North Carolina, and then developed new symptoms of a brain tumor. A magnetic resonance (MR) scan of the brain done at a local hospital revealed the presence of a large tumor in the right front part of the brain. This was removed and the patient was then sent to the University of North Carolina for postoperative radiation. Our task was complicated by the previous irradiation and the need to

avoid re-irradiation that tissue. Thus we needed to localize the tumor on our treatment planning CT with high precision but the planning CT showed no tumor at all, because it had been grossly removed. We were able to accomplish the following steps:

- 1) Create volume renderings and digitally reconstructed radiographs of the patient from the CT data and use them to register the planning CT with the patient.
- 2) Register the 3D MR data set with the planning CT.
- 3) Create an interactive 3D composite of the preoperative MR and postoperative CT to check the degree of this registration.
- 4) Transfer the tumor volume from the MR to the CT.
- 5) Calculate a wide variety of treatment plans (dose calculations) from the CT/MR data.
- 6) Select the best treatment plan, one that gets most of the radiation dose into the tumor remnant and little into the previously irradiated volume of brain

As we will show, Steps 1-3 and 5 are extremely compute intensive, and, for all intents and purposes, could not have been accomplished until recently. The patient has just finished treatment and is expected to do well.

In summary, radiation therapy treatment planning has benefited greatly from advances in high end computing. In turn, this medical discipline has simulated much research into image processing and display.

CHARLES S PESKIN

BIOGRAPHY

Charles S. Peskin was born on April 15, 1946, in New York City. He received an A.B. in Engineering and Applied Physics from Harvard University (1968) and a Ph.D. in Physiology from the Albert Einstein College of Medicine (1972). He then joined the Courant Institute of Mathematical Sciences, New York University, where he has been a Professor of Mathematics since 1981. From 1983-1988 he was a MacArthur Fellow.

Peskin has worked on a wide range of problems in which mathematics and computing are applied to biology and medicine. Some examples are blood flow in the heart, computer-assisted design of prosthetic cardiac valves, fibre architecture of the heart and its valves, fluid dynamics of the inner ear, photon noise in vision and nuclear medicine, voltage-dependent gating in nerve membrane channels, control of copy number in bacterial plasmids, simulation of a quantum effect in classical molecular dynamics computations, and Brownian ratchet dynamics of molecular intracellular machinery. The common goal of these various projects is to understand the function of living systems in mathematical and in computational terms.

THREE-DIMENSIONAL COMPUTATION OF BLOOD FLOW IN THE HEART

Dr Charles S Peskin

Courant Institute of Mathematical
Sciences

New York University

ABSTRACT

To study the problem of blood flow in the cardiac chambers, it is necessary to take into account the mechanical properties of the muscular heart walls and the flexible heart valve leaflets. These tissues are fibre reinforced, and their fibre architecture plays a profound role in cardiac mechanics. In the case of the left ventricular wall, the muscle fibres have been described as geodesic curves on a nested family of toroidal surfaces. In the case of the arterial valves, the collagen fibres that support the valve leaflets have a branching, braided appearance that suggests a fractal geometry.

The first part of this lecture takes the fibre architecture of the heart as given and is concerned with the mathematical formulation and numerical solution of the equations of motion of the fibre-fluid system. A computational method known as the immersed boundary method will be described. This method has now been implemented in parallel/vector fashion on the Cray C-90 computer, where it is used to solve the equations of a three-dimensional fibre based model of the heart that includes right and left atria and ventricles, all four valves, and nearby segments of the great arteries and veins that attach to the heart. These vessels have blind ends in the model, but they are equipped with sources and sinks that can be used to apply appropriate pressure loads, or, indeed, to simulate the rest of the circulation. The three-dimensional heart model will be shown

in action in a computer-generated videotape. In the construction of such a model, it is helpful to have a mathematical theory of the fibre architecture of the heart.

The second part of the lecture therefore addresses the intriguing question whether the cardiac fibre structure can be deduced from mechanical considerations. Such theories will be briefly described for the axisymmetric left ventricular wall and for the fractal fibre architecture of the arterial valves. It is, however, an open question how to extend these anatomical theories to the atrioventricular valves and to the asymmetric geometry of the heart as a whole.

PRZEMYSŁAW PRUSINKIEWICZ BIOGRAPHY

Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz is Professor of Computer Science at the University of Calgary. He has been conducting research in computer graphics since the late 1970s. In 1985, he originated a method for visualizing the structure and the development of plants based on L-systems, a mathematical model of development. He is a co-author of three textbooks and two monographs, "Lindenmayer systems, Fractals, and Plants" (Springer-Verlag 1989) and "The Algorithmic Beauty of Plants" (Springer-Verlag 1990), as well as approximately 50 technical papers. His current work is focused on mathematical models of growth and pattern formation in living organisms.

Professor Prusinkiewicz holds an M.S. and Ph.D., both in Computer Science, from the Technical University of Warsaw. Before joining the faculty of the University of Calgary in 1991, he was Professor at the University of Regina, Assistant Professor at the University of Science and Technology of Algiers, and Assistant Professor at the University of Warsaw. He was also a Visiting Professor at Yale University (1988), at L'Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne (1990), and an invited researcher at the University of Bremen (1989).

Professor Prusinkiewicz collaborates with many researchers in computer graphics and theoretical biology worldwide.

MODELING AND VISUALIZATION OF BIOLOGICAL STRUCTURES IN A VIRTUAL LABORATORY

Dr Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz
Department of Computer Science
The University of Calgary
Calgary, Alberta, Canada T2N 1N4

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ABSTRACT

Rapid progress in the modeling of biological structures and simulation of development has occurred over the last few years. It has been coupled with the visualization of simulation results, which has led to a better understanding of morphogenesis and given rise to new procedural techniques for realistic image synthesis. In my presentation, I propose to review the recent body of work on models of biological structures with a significant visual component. The topics include:

- 1) The role of photorealism in the models of biological structures,
- 2) Classification of visual models of morphogenesis,
- 3) Reaction-diffusion models (animal coat patterns, shell pigmentation patterns),
- 4) Diffusion-limited aggregation and growth (models of bacterial colonies, developmental models of corals and sponges),
- 5) Cellular- and voxel-automata models (climbing plants, models of roots),
- 6) L-system-based models of plants (herbaceous plants and trees).

The last topic will be covered in particular detail due to the prospective application of the results in computer-assisted landscape architecture, the design of new varieties of plants, and computer-assisted teaching and research in botany.

The presentation will be illustrated using computer-generated images, animations

of modeled structures, and demonstration of the interactive simulation software.

JOHN FURNESS

BIOGRAPHY

Australian, born 1945

B.Sc (physics and mathematics, Uni of Melb.), 1966

M.Sc (physiology, zoology dept, Uni of Melb.), 1969

Ph.D (physiology, zoology dept, Uni of Melb.), 1971

Physiology Dept, Birmingham UK 1971-1973

Zoology, Melb. 1974

Anatomy and Histology, Flinders University, 1975 to 1990, Professor and Head of Department, 1984-1990.

Professor of Physiology, Melbourne U 1990-1992

Professor of Anatomy and Cell Biology, Melbourne U 1993-

(During these appointments, spent time as Fulbright Fellow, National Institute of Mental Health, Washington, DC, 1979-1980; Visiting Fellow, Cornell Medical Center, New York, 2 months in 1981; Visiting Scientist, UCLA, 4 months, 1989).

Awards, responsibilities (part list); Exhibition in Zoology (1969), Fellow of Australian Academy (elected 1989), Janssen Research Award (1993), Distinguished Research Prize Australian Gastroenterology Society (1994); currently and editorial board member for 7 journals, member, Biological Sciences Panel of ARC (1990-1992); member, Scientific Advisory Board, Walter and Eliza Hall Institute, member Advisory Committee, Mental Health Research Institute. Holder (with Joel Bornstein), NH&MRC Program Grant.

Publications: 280 scientific articles, 1 book.

REALISTIC MODELS OF THE NERVOUS SYSTEM: ARE THEY ACHIEVABLE AND WILL THEY BE USEFUL?

John B Furness, Joel C Bornstein, Hugh Kelly, Wolf A A Kunze and Robert A R Bywater, Departments of Anatomy and Cell Biology, and Physiology, University of Melbourne, Department of Physiology, Monash University.

ABSTRACT

One of the most challenging of all questions is to understand how the complex operations of the brain are achieved. Of course, understanding can occur at several levels, but, to many physiologists, a demonstration that an adequate level of understanding has been attained would include being able to break the brain, or at least part of the nervous system, down to its constituent elements, the neurons, and be able to simulate the properties of the whole system, from experimentally determined properties of the neurons and their connections. This alone may not be sufficient. If a simple function, involving few neurons, were modelled, the solution may be trivial. A two neuron reflex, such as the tendon jerk, might yield little understanding of integration in more complex systems. Thus, the part of the nervous system that is simulated must have sufficient size and complexity that the outcome of simulation has unpredictable elements. Thus, the model itself becomes an experimental tool.

We have chosen to model the nervous system of the intestine, in relation to its role in controlling propulsion of its contents. The details of the modelling are presented in the demonstration at this meeting. We have set out to produce a model that is applicable to nervous systems in general, that is

parameters can be set within the model that allow any nervous system, or functionally separable part of a nervous system, to be modelled. We have chosen the enteric nervous system to validate our approach because this is possibly the only mammalian system for which sufficient experimental data exists to test the model.

The utility of such models cannot be adequately evaluated until successful large scale model, such as ours, are run successfully. At this stage, the model is being run with up to 50,000 neurons and produces physiologically valid outputs. With further refinement, we expect the model to be instrumental in predicting and defining properties of this nerve circuit and to be capable of predicting drug interactions and pathological outcomes in complex regions of the mammalian nervous system.

This work is supported by the NH & MRC.

JIM WRIGHT

BIOGRAPHY

J.J.Wright holds a joint appointment at the Swinburne Center for Applied Neuroscience (where he holds a Professorial Fellowship) and the Mental Health Research Institute of Victoria (where he is Director of the Brain Dynamics Laboratory).

His primary training is in medicine, and psychiatry. He has been involved in research work on the EEG since the 1970's, when he was a research fellow at the California Institute of Technology. He was formerly Head of the Department of Psychiatry in the School of Medicine, at the University of Auckland.

SIMULATION OF ELECTROCORTICAL WAVES USING ANATOMICAL ESTIMATES OF SYNAPTIC DENSITY

Dr James J.Wright

Swinburne University of Technology
Centre for Applied Neuroscience
Hawthorn, Victoria, Australia

e-mail: jjw@brain.physics.swin.oz.au

ABSTRACT

Estimates of the connectivity and synaptic densities of real cortical neurones have enabled us to specify a lumped neural network, in which synaptic densities appear as additive coupling weights, and axo-dendritic processes as delays. Action potential density follows a sigmoidal relation to dendritic, or local field, potential.

The network reproduces spectral, autoregression, wave-velocity and frequency-wavenumber properties of real electrocortical waves, including all the major cerebral rhythms.

The single control parameter is the strength of diffuse driving input - an effect analogous to the action of the non-specific reticular-activating system of the brain; a neural system which controls the properties of the EEG, and the correlated state of consciousness.

ROBERT C. BELL

BIOGRAPHY

Robert C. Bell was born in Hobart, Tas, but has lived for most of his life in Melbourne. He attended Monash University, where he received a BSc (Hons) and a PhD in Applied Mathematics.

From 1974 to 1990, he worked at the CSIRO Division of Atmospheric Research, providing mathematical and computing support for research in the dynamics of the atmosphere. From 1987 to 1990, he was the Computing Group Leader.

In 1990, he was appointed to the position of CSIRO Supercomputing Support Manager, and in 1992 to the position of CSIRO Supercomputing Facility Manager.

SUPERCOMPUTING FOR YOU IN AUSTRALIA

Dr Robert C Bell

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723 Swanston St Carlton VIC 3053

e-mail: robert.bell@mel.dit.csiro.au

ABSTRACT

This talk will highlight some of the trends in High Performance Computing, and outline the facilities available to scientists in Australia. Particular emphasis will be placed upon the CSIRO Supercomputing Facility, and software for life sciences.

Around the world, many countries are emphasising the value of HPC systems for scientific and industrial research and development. The USA is leading with its HPCC and NII initiatives, but there are new and expanding centres in Europe and E and SE Asia.

In Australia, there are HPC centres in most 'old' universities, and in many others, with consortia being formed, for example the Ormond Centre linking The University of Melbourne and RMIT. In CSIRO, a number of Divisions have significant facilities, and there is the central CSIRO Supercomputing Facility (CSF).

At the core of the CSF are the Cray Y-MP 4E with 4 processors, and the Storage Technology Corporation Automated Cartridge system running under the control of Cray Research's Data Migration Facility.

The CSIRO Cray is

- sustaining 350 Mflop/s (peak is 1.3 Gflop/s)

- highly reliable (available for all except two of the office hours in the first year of operation)
- well utilised (>98%)
- supporting research in 15 Divisions regularly

The CSF has a Support Group of four staff, and a Help Desk.

The policy framework allows access under Divisional control, without additional peer group review, as is necessary for access to USA NSF centres.

The funding framework allows access to users without hidden or unbudgeted costs. The core of the CSF is centrally funded. User Divisions contribute to a Development Fund (which is used to enhance the CSF), and receive a share of the capacity in proportion to their contribution.

The CSF has software to support life science applications. Suppliers include Cray Research, Gaussian, BIOSYM, and Teijin/MSI.

The mission of the CSF and Support Group is to provide the best facility, software and support possible for CSIRO science and industry research.

ANNELIESE F PALMER

**BIOSYM TECHNOLOGIES INC.
APPLICATIONS SCIENTIST FOR
ASIA/PACIFIC REGION**

BIOGRAPHY

Anneliese completed her PhD in 1992 entitled "Molecular Modelling of HIV-1 Protease", under the supervision of Professor Peter Andrews, at the Centre for Drug Design and Development, University of Queensland, Australia. The work involved the use of Biosym software and other receptor-based inhibitor design techniques to assist in the design and optimization of HIV-1 Protease inhibitors. A series of peptidic inhibitors were then synthesised by solid phase synthesis and assayed for HIV-1 Protease inhibitors, to validate the theoretical modelling techniques.

Anneliese was employed by Biosym Technologies in mid 1991 as an applications scientist while completing the final stages of her PhD to provide technical support for the rapidly growing user base in the Asia/Pacific region. Anneliese is based in Biosym's Sydney office and is a frequent visitor to Korea, Japan, Taiwan, China, Malaysia, Singapore, India, Thailand and New Zealand. Anneliese's expertise is largely in the area of Biosym's Life Sciences suite of software tools with practical experience in drug design and protein modelling. While at Biosym she has carried out various drug design projects for several pharmaceutical companies in Asia.

BIOSYM TECHNOLOGIES

Presented by

Dr Anneliese Palmer
Biosym Technologies, Inc.
North Sydney, NSW, Australia

BIOSYM Technologies is the leading supplier of Computer Aided Molecular Design (CAMD) software for applications in biopharmaceuticals, chemicals, polymers, catalysts, and advanced materials.

CAMD enables researchers to gain a better understanding of chemical behaviour at the molecular level, and to correlate experimental data with chemical structure. Through graphical simulation, researchers are able to try a vast array of ideas and quickly focus on the most promising research avenues.

The arena of commercial CAMD software development has progressed rapidly over the last ten years and BIOSYM has traditionally led the market place through active research consortia, bringing together key scientists from commercial and non profit organisations to direct the development of rigorous 'state of the art' software to meet the requirements in a particular area. This has been a proven formula for success in the development of software for Polymer Property Prediction; Catalyst, Sorbtion and inorganic systems, and more recently for the simulation of Electronic, Optic and Magnetic materials. Additional projects have been established for the development Macromolecular Crystallographic tools, Organometallic systems, and in the simulation of Solvation Effects.

To meet the ever increasing challenges in Life Sciences research, BIOSYM has a

broad spectrum of individual software tools including-

INSIGHT II - Advanced graphics interface for all modelling applications including multiple model building and display capabilities, and acting as a single interface to all the following molecules:-

DISCOVER - Molecular mechanics and Dynamics simulations of small molecules and macromolecular systems, utilising several force field methodologies.

APEX 3D - The next generation in activity prediction for Biological Systems (lead generation in drug design utilising QSAR and Pharmacophore prediction).

LUDI - State of the art De Novo ligand design for known and unknown receptor surfaces.

DELPHI - Rigorous electrostatic calculations for solvated systems.

HOMOLOGY - Protein Structure prediction by structural and sequence Homology.

PROFILES 3D - Macromolecular structure validation based on predicted conformational profiles.

CONSENSUS - Automatic, one step approach for Homology model building.

SEARCH/COMPARE - Systematic conformational searches and volume comparisons.

SKETCHER - 2D sketch to 3D structure *via* distance geometry.

NMR Refinement - Integrated suite of tools for biomacromolecular structure determination from NMR-derived

distance and dihedral restraints (also includes simulated annealing techniques incorporating BIOSYM's *DISCOVER* program).

FELIX 1D/2D and ND - Processing, display and analyses of all types of high resolution, solid state, *in vivo*, 1D to 4D homonuclear and heteronuclear NMR data.

FELIX MODEL - Direct interaction between experimental NOSEY data, structure and back calculated NOSEY data within a integrated interface.

FELIX ASSIGN - Automatic and semi-automatic tools for NMR spectral assignment of biomacromolecules.

ZINDO - A semi-Empirical Molecular Orbital program parameterised for spectroscopic properties of molecules.

DMol - Advanced Quantum Mechanics based on Local Density Functional Theory.

TURBOMOLE - *ab initio* electronic structure calculations using the SCF level of theory.

During this meeting we would like to demonstrate these tools and discuss how BIOSYM, through active collaboration and direct application, may augment existing experimental and theoretical research techniques.

THOMAS J. HOFFEL

MOLECULAR SIMULATIONS

San Diego, California, USA

BIOGRAPHY

M.Sc (Chemistry), Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, 1990.

B.Sc (Chemistry), (Hons.) University of Michigan-Dearborn, 1987.

Extensive research, understanding and interest in the areas of free energy simulation, thermodynamic perturbation methods, and general molecular modelling techniques as applied to protein, small molecules and other biological systems.

In-depth knowledge of current molecular simulation, QSAR, and graphics software packages, namely CHARMM, Quanta, Sybyl, SAS and Anacondas. Familiarity with other molecular mechanics/dynamics/graphics software packages (Mopac, Gaussian, Insight/Discover, Amber, MACCS, XPLOR...etc).

Strong background in statistical mechanics, thermodynamics and general physical chemistry.

Broad-based background in the user of state-of-the-art computing facilities: Cray, Silicon Graphics and Vax systems as well as Alliant, Multiflow, IBM, Evans and Sutherland graphics workstations.

Natural ability to conduct self-motivated research, apply novel theory to real-world problems, and interact well with researchers in varying fields.

July 1993-present: Applications Scientist, Molecular Simulations Inc., San Diego. Responsibilities include contract research, software evaluation/validation, and

customer demonstrations/technical support.

June 1991-July 1993: Computational chemist, DowBlanco, Indianapolis, Indiana. Extensive involvement in projects encompassing multiple aspects of experimental design for the development of novel pesticides.

TEIJIN-MOLECULAR SIMULATIONS, INC.

Presented by

Thomas Hoeffel

MOLECULAR SIMULATIONS - SOLUTIONS THROUGH SIMULATION

ABSTRACT

Computational modelling at the molecular and atomic scale has become an established research method. The ability to develop molecular level hypotheses based on computational experiments provides the discovery scientist with a mechanistic understanding of the chemical system being studied. While a great deal can be gained from 3D visualisation of molecular systems, it is simulation which provides the understanding which can lead to the predictive capability required for the development of novel compounds.

Molecular Simulations Inc. has a comprehensive suite of molecular modelling software for Life Science applications.

These simple to use software modules include:

QUANTA/CHARMM - provides an environment for the generation, editing and visualisation of the initial model of

the system to be studied. CHARMM's well validated energy and force calculations form the core of the molecular mechanics and dynamics capability of this combination.

Software modules include:

- Protein Modelling
- Protein Health
- STAR-X-ray Structure Analysis
- Electrostatics & Brownian Dynamics Simulations
- NM2 Interface
- NMR Structure Determination
- NMR Compass
- NMR Pipe

POLARIS - represents a major advance for calculations of solvation free energies and electrostatic properties of molecules and macromolecules in solution and can be applied to applications in drug design, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, medicinal chemistry, protein engineering, agrochemical and food research.

QUNATA software and Computational modules may be simply configured to meet the exact requirements of the Computational and Molecular Modelling Scientist.

PROTEIN WORKBENCH - integrates the full features of QUANTA to create a complete environment for protein homology, side chain mutation and loop generations, molecular dynamics and minimisation and extensive protein structural analysis. Consequently it has application in solving problems in structure determination, protein engineering, antibody modelling or rational drug design.

NMR WORKBENCH - integrates the full features of QUANTA to create an integrated system that combines interactive multi-dimensional spectra analysis and advanced molecular

modelling methods to provide a streamlined process of data extraction and structure prediction with increased accuracy and throughput.

QUANTA Software and Computational Modules provide the most flexibility in supported workstation platforms. QUANTA is designed for use on one or more workstations running a version of the UNIX operating system and is supported on the following platforms.

- DEC™ 3000 AXP™ workstation with ZLX or Denali graphics options, running the DEC OSF/2™ operating system, version 1.3.
- Hewlett-Packard 9000 Series 700 workstations with 24CRXZ or 48CRXZ graphics options, running the HP-UX operating system, release A.09.01 or later.
- IBM® RISC System/6000™ workstations with GT4 graphics option, running AIX™ operating system, release 3.2.5 or later.
- Silicon Graphics® workstation with 24 bit Z-buffered graphics capabilities, running IRIX™ operating system, release 4.0.5 or later.

The following modules are also available for installation on CRAY computers; CHARMM™, FARM/CHARM™, X-PLOR/Refine™, X-PLOR/DG™, X-PLOR/BOTH™.

MAREK T. MICHALEWICZ

BIOGRAPHY

Born in 1957 in Wroclaw, Poland. He studied physics at Wroclaw University from 1976 to 1981.

He emigrated to Australia in late 1981 and continued physics studies at La Trobe University, Melbourne (1982 M.Sc. Prelim.)

1984: M.Sc. degree from LaTrobe University (theoretical physics);
1997 Ph.D. in theoretical condensed matter physics from The Australian National University in Canberra.

1997-88: computer consultant for the Federal Government Department and the Real Estate Industry in Canberra. During that period he was also a Visiting Fellow, at the Dep. of Theoretical Physics, The ANU.

1988 to 1990: Research Associate at the School of Physics and Astronomy, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, USA.

In 1990 he joined Supercomputing Support Group in the Division of Information Technology, CSIRO in Melbourne, where he is now a Senior Research Scientist. He is involved in consulting work on multi-disciplinary Supercomputing projects in computational chemistry, materials science and physics.

He continues research work in condensed matter physics. His research interests encompass:

condensed matter theory, surface theory; surface electronic and collective properties; plasmons; theory of scanning tunneling; liquid state theory; electronic properties of disordered transition metal

oxides; fullerenes, plasmon modes, spheres, shells, etc., computational methods in physics, algorithms, parallel computations in physics and computational quantum chemistry.

UNICHEM SOFTWARE FROM CRAY RESEARCH, INC.

Presented by

Marek T. Michalewicz
CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group
Division of Information Technology
723 Swanston St Carlton VIC 3053

e-mail: marek@mel.dit.csiro.au

UniChem is an easy-to-use supercomputing environment for computational chemistry. The primary uses of UniChem's are in chemical, pharmaceutical, petrochemical and chemical physics research as well as in automotive, electronics or aerospace industries. UniChem is a distributed environment: a graphical user interface resides on a Silicon Graphics workstation and the computational part on Cray supercomputers.

UniChem is one of the most sophisticated, advanced and user-friendly computational molecular quantum chemistry software products available today. As such it will be useful in all fields of chemical research, both pure and applied. The development consortium, apart from Cray Research, included industrial partners: Du Pont, Monsanto and its subsidiaries G.D. Searle and NutraSweet, Eli Lilly, Exxon and 3M. The application areas could easily be deduced from this list of sponsors. Explicitly the key application areas of UniChem include drug design,

agrochemicals, polymers, catalysis, speciality chemicals, environmental studies, advanced structural, optical, electronic and magnetic materials and many others.

The computational part of UniChem consists of three high-performance, state of the art programs, each designed for specific type of calculations.

MNDO91

The MNDO91 is a semi-empirical program developed over the last twenty or so years by Walter Thiel and co-workers in the University of Wuppertal in Germany. The acronym stands for the modified neglect of differential overlap, a method in which some of the diatomic two-center electron-electron integrals representing the repulsion are set to zero (neglected). The Hamiltonian is balanced by introducing the experimental data for the energy expression, usually derived from the x-ray diffraction on molecules of similar geometry and composition.

The MNDO91 is dominated by matrix operations; the algorithm scales like N^3 . The method is very efficient and fast. Recently a 540-atom carbon cluster was calculated using MNDO90, achieving the speed of 2.2 GFLOPS on Cray Y-MP supercomputer.

A researcher can select a model Hamiltonian: MNDO, AM1, PM3, or older methods like MNDO/H, MNDOC, MINDO3 and CNDO/2.

The calculations, depending on the choice of input parameters may include: geometry optimization, energy, gradient and transition state search, force constants. One can select molecular orbitals (either HOMO, LUMO or up to 10 highest occupied and 5 lowest

unoccupied). Thermodynamic properties such as heat capacity, free energy, entropy and enthalpy can be calculated at ten standard temperatures (273.15, 298.15, 300 and every 100 centigrade up to 1000K) or at 25 temperatures, where the user has to specify the minimum, temperature increase, and the number of intervals to be included in the calculations. MNDO90 is applicable to molecules containing up to approximately 500 atoms.

DGauss

DGauss is an ab initio density functional program applicable to molecules and clusters containing up to approximately 200 atoms, including elements from hydrogen to xenon, developed by Jan W. Andzelm at Cray Research. DGauss, unlike the Hartree-Fock method, takes into account the electron correlations, hence it is particularly well suited for metals, transition metals and inorganic systems. A researcher has a choice of global orbital and auxiliary basis sets (DZVP, DZVP2, TZVP, Pople, and A1, A2, A3, P1 respectively). The calculations may include the non-local correction after the final self consistent step (Becke-Perdew or Becke-Stoll-Preuss-Pavlidou).

The calculated properties include the optimized geometry, molecular orbitals (either HOMO, LUMO or up to 10 highest occupied and 5 lowest unoccupied), total electron density, spin density and electrostatic potential.

DGauss is applicable to molecules and clusters containing up to approximately 200 atoms. DGauss is well suited for metals, transition metals and both organic and inorganic systems.

CADPAC

CADPAC is an ab initio Hartree-Fock program developed by R. Amos and co-workers at the University of Cambridge,

England, applicable to systems containing up to 50 atoms. CADPAC module is comparable in methodology and functionality to Gaussian90. It appears that CADPAC has larger number of different basis of functions and the user interface makes it much easier to use than Gaussian90.

The Hartree-Fock basis sets include some twenty different choices, depending on the type of atom and the orbital. A user can also define his own basis sets. Some of the molecular properties obtained for the Hartree-Fock CADPAC program at final, optimized geometry are: static polarizability and hyperpolarizability, magnetic susceptibility and dynamic polarizability and hyperpolarizability.

CADPAC is applicable to systems containing up to 50 atoms.

At present CSIRO is the only institution in Australia that has the UniChem license. We will describe the UniChem in some detail and present the CSIRO experience with the software.

MAPMAKER: A VERSATILE TOOL FOR CONSTRUCTING GENETIC LINKAGE MAPS.

Presented by

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In recent years considerable progress has been made in the construction of genetic linkage maps of several species. The rapid development of molecular markers and genetic mapping populations complemented by computational analysis of genetic linkage are major contributors to this progress.

The use of a common reference genetic mapping population among different research groups and computerization of genetic loci data has accelerated the pace from global genomic scans to saturated mapping of targeted genetic regions.

The MAPMAKER program has been widely used in genetic linkage analysis. A stepwise illustration beginning from different types of experimental populations, types of genetic polymorphism, creation of raw data files, two point and multipoint analysis leading to the construction of the best likelihood genetic map will be demonstrated. How to recognise potential artifacts in the best likelihood maps generated by MAPMAKER in genomic regions with chromosomal rearrangements will also be demonstrated.

PLEXUS

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A REALISTIC COMPUTER SIMULATION OF A MAMMALIAN NEURAL CIRCUITRY

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We present a demonstration of a computer simulation of the operation of the neuronal circuitry that controls propulsive reflexes in the intestine. A general program, Plexus© that could be used for any nervous system, has been written in C for operation on a Sun SPAC 2 computer. The resting and dynamic properties of neurons have been modelled in terms of experimentally determined biophysical properties. Transients are driven by conductance changes and depicted as variations in membrane potential. Individual neurons are assigned to sensory, motor and inter-neuron classes in proportion to experimentally determined ratios for the guinea-pig small intestine. Positions of nerve cell bodies, directions and lengths of projections and connectivity in the simulation match those that have been determined experimentally. The program can be used to model different lengths and numbers of neurons. At this stage, 30,000 to 50,000 neurons in an area of 1.5 cm (circumferential) and up to 10 cm in length are typically used.

Outcomes are displayed by highlighting active cell bodies in a plan view of the myenteric plexus and by plots of temporal changes in membrane potentials of individual neurons. The program simulates the responses of neurons that have been recorded using intracellular microelectrodes. We will use the simulation as an experimental tool, for example, to predict the effects of drugs acting at specified sites and to determine boundary conditions for parameters that cannot be determined directly by biological experimentation. Thus, the simulation is an important experimental tool in its own right.

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Fatma has worked as an Information Specialist for 8 years, and has been with CSIRO for the past 11 months.

Part of her time is spent representing STN by acting on the help desk and giving STN courses. The rest of her time is spent in the Search Party area, where she finds information for people both internal and external to the organisation.

STN International

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GENESIS

presented by

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GENESIS (General Neural Simulation System) is a general purpose numerical simulator designed to facilitate the modelling of neural networks. Developed at CALTECH over the past 5 years it is one of the most sophisticated and flexible neuronal simulators available. GENESIS through a GUI and an efficient script language, allows the specification of neuronal models that range over a wide range of scales - from complex multicompartment single neuronal models to very large scale neural networks. This is achieved through a modular design in which the individual building blocks are linked together to create the final simulation. These objects are discrete components that interact with each other in a predefined manner. Typical objects include compartments, objects that attempt to mimick the passive properties of a section of dendrite and transmitter and voltage activated channels.

GENESIS is designed to run under UNIX and X windows. To date it has been ported to not less than 10 machine architectures including an Intel parallel machine.

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